

BUTTERFLY MORPHOLOGY**Abdullayeva Mexriban Rayimberganovna**

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Annatotion: This article describes the bioecology of butterfly morphology in detail. the benefits and harms of its importance in nature to agriculture are highlighted.

Key words: Butterfly, fossil, pigmet, larva, sensation, morphology

Butterflies, lepidoptera (Lepidoptera) are a group of insects that develop by complete metamorphosis. Originated at the beginning of the Mesozoic; the main families were formed at the beginning of the Paleogene. Fossil remains are known mainly from the Cretaceous period. The mouthparts of most butterflies consist of a highly specialized suction tube that spirals around the underside of the head. The membranous wings are covered with colored scales. The color of the wings, especially their different colors, is due to the absorption of light by the colorless scales at different angles, and the black, yellow and other colored spots are due to the pigment. The shape and length of their whiskers are different. The recorded wingspan is from 3.2 mm (dwarf moths) to 300 mm (tuns). The shape of the eggs is different and has systematic importance. Worms have 5 pairs of false abdominal legs along with 3 pairs of pectoral legs. The cones are closed (mostly, in a cocoon), open (free) in the representatives of the bottom. Butterflies are generally divided into the suborders of butterflies (equal wings) and butterflies (different wings). In some cases, toothed moths with gnawing mouthparts are divided into a separate subfamily. The system of the family of butterflies is not clearly developed, it is divided into 100 to 200 families. About 140,000 species are known. The fauna of butterflies is especially diverse in the tropical region. About 1500 species have been identified in Uzbekistan. Families of butterflies, moths, leafhoppers, fireflies, and moths are particularly rich in species..

Most butterflies are active in the evening or at night, and some are active during the day. Adult butterflies feed on flower nectar or plant (sometimes aphid) sap. Most butterfly imagos have reduced mouthparts and do not feed (aphagi). Toothed beetles feed on pollen. Butterflies live as adults from a few days, even a few hours (non-feeding species) to several months (adult hibernating butterflies). The worms of most butterflies are phytophagous, but there are also saprophages, keratophages (yung and leaf-eaters), predators, and even parasites (in the tropics). The annual growth cycle varies; most species (monovoltines) produce flowers once a year, others (bi- and polyvoltines) produce seeds twice or more; the generation of species that develop in the woody part of trees lasts 2-3 years. Usually, some species hibernate during the larval stage, imago or egg stage. Diapause of some species takes place in different periods of development. Some butterflies, especially desert species, also go into diapause on the ground. Many butterflies (mostly, specialized ones) participate in pollination of plants. Mulberry, ailant, and Chinese oak silkworm butterflies are hand-reared to obtain silk. Most moths (moths, moths, etc.) cause significant damage to agricultural crops, forestry (weavers, leafhoppers, etc.), food supplies, and wool and fur products (moths, moths, etc.).

In Uzbekistan, more than 100 species of butterflies damage fruit trees and valuable wild plants. Some species (for example, autumn, callow, cotton, small landworms, etc.) are pests of cotton and related crops. Many butterflies, especially diurnal species, are in dramatic decline due to habitat destruction and the use of toxic chemicals and fertilizers. Several species of butterflies are protected.

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